

Country deep dive:
Finland

State of the European alternative protein research and innovation ecosystem

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Alternative protein research in Finland

Finland punches above its weight in the field, topping per capita investment and coming behind only the UK for overall government investment in fermentation.

However, the Finnish R&I ecosystem has seen variability in funding and is showing early signs of stagnation in outputs. Without increased effort to outline a path for the research community, Finland risks not capitalising on its early embrace of the field.

What do we mean by alternative protein pillars?

The fields of research that are the focus of this report are split into three main ‘pillars’, described below. In some instances, research projects combine techniques from across these disciplines. These are referred to as ‘cross-cutting’ throughout the report.

Plant-based

Produced directly from plants but look, taste, and cook like conventional animal products. For the purposes of this report, traditional fermentation techniques that use yeast or other microorganisms to modify the flavour, texture, or other characteristics of plant proteins will be considered within the plant-based pillar.

Image: THIS

Fermentation

Used in two primary ways: **Biomass fermentation** leverages the fast growth and high protein content of microorganisms to produce large quantities of protein. **Precision fermentation** uses microbes to produce specific functional ingredients important for the manufacture of alternative protein end products.

Image: Revo Foods

Cultivated

Foods like chicken, pork, beef, and fish that are produced by cultivating animal cells directly, thus replicating the sensory and nutritional profiles of conventional meat and seafood.

Image: Parima

Cross-cutting

In some instances, research projects combine techniques from across these disciplines. For example, research projects on cellular agriculture, the combined approaches of precision fermentation and cultivated meat development, or research on an aspect of the entirety of the alternative protein field, such as a social science question.

Finnish funding compared to governments across Europe

Investment from the top 10 governments funding alternative proteins in Europe, 2020-2025, showing total public funding* (excluding nonprofit contributions) and funding per capita.** Finland ranks fourth in total funding, but first on a per capita basis.

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

*Funding for some countries, such as the Netherlands, France, and Belgium, is likely an underestimate. **Per capita spending is only shown for the top 10 countries by total public research funding. Note that this is not a ranking of the top 10 by per capita spending, and that some countries in the top 10 by per capita spending are not displayed.

A regional funding overview

Investment from the Nordic region, broken down by jurisdiction of funder (including nonprofit funders), 2020-2025.

Some variation in funding was seen across the period, but there was continued interest from all four countries. Finland showed the most variability.

Finnish funders

Investment in Finland, by research funder, with inset showing research category, 2020-2025.

Finnish investment has varied over the period, with a bumper year in 2024, but a decline in 2025. Fermentation and cross-cutting funding to technologies such as cellular agriculture have largely been the beneficiaries.

Publications: overall trends

This chart shows the overall trends in academic publications in peer-reviewed journals on topics related to alternative proteins in the period 2020-2025.

Finland has contributed to 184 publications on topics related to alternative proteins in the period 2020-2025 and ranks 11th overall in Europe.

Publication output grew by 18% per year on average but was relatively stagnant from 2022.

There were 38 research publications in 2025 compared with 19 in 2020 – a 100% increase.

Breakdown of publications by alternative protein pillar:

- 65% plant-based proteins
- 12% fermentation-made proteins and ingredients
- 9% cultivated meat and seafood
- 15% cross-cutting topics

Leading research-performing organisations

This map shows the leading institutions for alternative protein research in Finland on the basis of unique publications in the period 2020-2025.

The most highly ranked Finnish organisation is the University of Helsinki which ranked 12th for total publications in 2025 and 6th overall for the period 2020-2025.

Finland ranks outside the top 10 in Europe for total plant-based and fermentations publications, coming in at 11th and 13th, respectively. However, it ranks 9th for cultivated meat and seafood.

Patents: overall trends

This chart shows the overall number of alternative protein patents published by Finnish innovators in the years 2015-2025 inclusive, stratified by alternative protein pillar.

The number of patents published fell in recent years, peaking at 83 in 2023.

There were 412 total patents published by Finnish innovators in the period 2015-2025 – the 7th highest total in Europe.

Breakdown of patents by alternative protein pillar:

- 73% plant-based proteins
- 22% fermentation-made proteins and ingredients
- 2% cultivated meat and seafood
- 3% cross-cutting topics

Patents: overall trends

This chart shows trends in unique patent families and cumulative patent filings by Finnish innovators in the years 2015-2025 inclusive, along with the cumulative number of patents that have been granted.

Priority filings – the very first filing on a new invention – have been rising slowly since 2015 and peaked at 15 in 2023.

Overall, a total of 412 patents have been filed since 2015, with 2022 seeing the highest number of filings at 87.

The number of patents granted has also risen, reaching 10 in 2025, with 37 patents granted in total.

Deep-dive: Plant-based

This section breaks down funding, publications, and patent trends, using research categories to explore strengths and weaknesses in the field of plant-based meat, seafood, eggs and dairy in Finland.

Research categories: Plant-based

Crop development

Breeding of crops and increased use of underutilised protein crops for higher protein yields and functionality.

Ingredient optimisation

Improved protein fractionation and functionalisation for higher-quality ingredients with less processing, and development of novel ingredients to augment nutritional profiles and enhance sensory experience.

End product formulation

Formulation and product design, including fat integration, shelf life, stability, sensory quality, and nutritional assessment and fortification.

Impact assessments

Includes life cycle, techno-economic, environmental, social, and geopolitical impact analyses.

Health and nutrition

Dietary impacts of alternative proteins including population-wide studies, systematic reviews, and in vitro studies on health impacts such as bioavailability.

Texturisation methods

Process innovations, including (but not limited to) novel texturisation methods such as extrusion, electrospinning, 3D printing, and enzymatic processing to match the texture of animal protein.

Food safety and quality

Toxicological and safety assessments, regulatory improvements, such as assay development or validation.

Consumer and market research

Consumer behaviour research including nomenclature studies, purchasing intent across retail and food environments, and market scoping and brand development.

Strain development

Screening and optimisation of novel strains to identify the most efficient pathways for producing targets or modifying substrates.

Funding: research categories

Investment from Finland, broken down by research category, 2020-2025.

The €30 million investment in ‘Multiple’ is the Business Finland investment, Valio’s ‘Food 2.0’. Investment in Finland has been somewhat patchy across many research areas, but bioprocess design is a clear research specialisation in the country.

Plant-based publications: research categories

This chart shows a breakdown by research category of Finnish academic publications on plant-based proteins in the years 2020-2025 inclusive.

Finnish researchers have mostly focused on ingredient optimisation (41% of all publications), followed by end product formulation (17%) and health & nutrition (10%).

Plant-based patents: research categories

This chart provides a breakdown of patent filings by Finnish innovators on technology areas related to plant-based proteins in the years 2015-2025 inclusive.

Finnish innovators filed patent applications mostly in relation to end product development (41% of all filings), texturisation methods (34%), and ingredient optimisation (25%).

Deep-dive: Fermentation

This section breaks down funding, publications, and patent trends, using research categories to explore strengths and weaknesses in the field of fermentation-enabled alternative proteins in Finland.

Research categories: Fermentation

Fermentation publications: research categories

This chart shows a breakdown by research category of Finnish academic publications on fermentation-made proteins and ingredients in the years 2020-2025 inclusive.

Impact assessments is the most common fermentation research category, accounting for 32%, followed by feedstocks and ingredient optimisation, both on 18%.

Fermentation patents: research categories

This chart provides a breakdown patent filings by Finnish innovators on technology areas related to fermentation-made proteins and ingredients in the years 2015-2025 inclusive.

Strain development is a unique strength of the Finnish fermentation ecosystem, accounting for (45%) of all patents.

Deep-dive: cultivated

This section breaks down funding, publications, and patent trends, using research categories to explore strengths and weaknesses in the field of cultivated meat and seafood in Finland.

Research categories: Cultivated

Cell line development

Sourcing, optimising, and banking new and existing cell lines to achieve faster growth, greater stability and stress tolerance, improved performance (including adherence and differentiation), and higher density across terrestrial and aquatic cell lines.

Bioprocess design

Innovations in bioreactor design and upstream/downstream processes to improve efficiency, monitoring, and control.

Texturisation methods

Developing techniques such as extrusion technology to replicate the fibrous, chewy textures of conventional meat and dairy.

Consumer market and research

Consumer behaviour research including nomenclature studies, purchasing intent across retail and food environments, and market scoping and brand development.

Food safety and quality

Toxicological and safety assessments, regulatory improvements, such as assay development or validation.

Scaffolding

Improved scaffolding biomaterials that support cell adherence and differentiation to allow the replication of complex animal meat structures.

Health and nutrition

Dietary impacts of alternative proteins including population-wide studies, systematic reviews, and in vitro studies on health impacts such as bioavailability.

Cell culture media

Reducing cell culture media costs and increasing their availability by characterising and validating novel sources of growth factors, amino acids, and other media components.

End product formulation

Formulation and product design, including fat integration, shelf life, stability, sensory quality, and nutritional assessment and fortification.

Impact assessments

Includes life cycle, techno-economic, environmental, social, and geopolitical impact analyses.

Cultivated publications: research categories

This chart shows a breakdown by research category of Finnish academic publications on cultivated meat and seafood in the years 2020-2025 inclusive.

Finnish cultivated meat and seafood researchers have mostly focused on impact assessments (50% of all publications) and consumer & market research (44%), with almost no publications on technical categories.

Cultivated patents: research categories

This chart provides a breakdown of patent filings by Finnish innovators on technology areas related to cultivated meat and seafood in the years 2015-2025 inclusive.

Finnish patent filings on cultivated meat and seafood have been limited to date and mostly focused on innovations in cell culture media.

Appendix and methods

Methodology

For full methods including search terms, inclusion and exclusion criteria and other technical details, please see the full technical appendix [here](#).

Funding

Data

Data sourced from GFI's publicly available global research funding database, the [GFI Research Grants Tracker](#), which houses information published by funders and research conductors globally. Kernel Science contributed to data retrieval. Funding information was also retrieved from [Dimensions.ai](#).

Time period

2010-2025. Data retrieved in February 2026.

Country focus

EU27 + Norway + Switzerland + UK.

Search strategy

A list of search terms was developed and [Dimensions.ai](#) results screened against predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria to identify those in scope for the study.

Grants focusing plant-based, fermentation-made, or cultivated proteins and ingredients meeting these criteria were analysed by title, recipient, funder country, pillar categorisation, end product and research sub-category.

Publications

Data

Data sourced from Dimensions, an interlinked research information system provided by Digital Science (<https://www.dimensions.ai>).

Time period

2020-2025. Data retrieved January 2026.

Country focus

EU27 + Norway + Switzerland + UK.

Search strategy

Complex search terms were devised that allowed us to trigger numerous publications that may be relevant to our analysis.

Search returns were screened against predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria to identify those in scope for the study.

Publications relevant to plant-based, fermentation-made, or cultivated proteins and ingredients meeting these criteria were analysed in the Dimensions Landscape & Discovery application and in spreadsheet format.

Patents

Data

Data sourced from Dimensions, an interlinked research information system provided by Digital Science (<https://www.dimensions.ai>).

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Key terminology: patents

Patent	An exclusive right granted for an invention that excludes others from making, using, offering for sale, or selling the invention. Patents benefit inventors by providing them with legal protection for their inventions. To receive this protection, they must publicly disclose details of the invention.
Patent family	A collection of patents covering the same or similar technical content disclosed by a common inventor(s) and patented in more than one country.
Priority date	Sometimes called the “effective filing date”, this is the first filing date in a family of patent applications and is used to establish the novelty and/or obviousness of a particular invention relative to other art. Each patent family will only have one priority date.
Filing date	The date when a patent application is first filed in the respective patent office. As there are no global patents, there may be numerous patent filings in different jurisdictions from the same patent family, each with its own filing date.
Publication date	The date on which the patent application is published (ie, the information is available to the public). This normally occurs approximately 18 months after the filing date.
Assignee	Organisation(s) and individual(s) that have an ownership interest in the legal rights a patent offers. An assignee is often the organisation employing the inventor of the technology. An assignee can also change at a later date.
Jurisdiction	The legal territory in which a patent is sought, for example, France, Spain, etc. Each patent must be filed with a national patent office in the country where protection is sought and there are no global patents.
Patent legal status	The current legal status of the patents, eg. ‘Granted’, ‘Active’, ‘Abandoned’, etc.

The patenting process

There are differences between patent offices in how a patent application is processed once it has been filed, but a general overview of the process is described in the table below.

For a more detailed explanation, please refer to [this resource](#) from the World Intellectual Property Organization. A detailed description of the European patent application process can be found [here](#).

1. Formal examination	The application is examined to ensure it complies with the administrative requirements set by the patent office.
2. Prior art search	A search is conducted to identify prior art that will be relevant in determining the patentability of the claimed invention.
3. Substantive examination	A more detailed examination is carried out to ensure the claimed invention satisfies the main criteria for patentability (patentable subject matter, novelty, inventive step, industrial applicability and sufficiency of disclosure).
4. Notification	Results of the examination are sent to the applicant or their legal representative and they are given an opportunity to respond to any objections raised.
5. Publication of patent application	The patent application is usually published approximately 18 months after the filing date.
6. Granting of patent	If the outcome of the examination is positive, the patent office grants the patent.
7. Publication of granted patent	The granted patent is published and the invention is disclosed to the public.
8. Pre-grant and/or post-grant opposition	Patent offices offer others the opportunity to oppose the grant of a patent, for example, if they believe the claimed invention is not new. Opposition proceedings can be held before or after the patent is granted.

About this report

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About GFI Europe

The Good Food Institute Europe is a nonprofit think tank helping to build a more sustainable, secure and just food system by diversifying protein production.

